

Devolving Work Responsibilities of School Heads: Accounts of Novice Teachers

Hazel A. Aquino

Abstract. This study explored the experiences of devolving work responsibilities of school heads: accounts of novice teachers. I get down the features and lines of the existing working responsibilities of their school heads, their effectiveness, and the teacher's coping practices on the challenges that come along the way. To achieve the objectives of the study, I made use of phenomenology. The 10 participants of this study are from Tagbaros Elementary School, Maco South District, Davao De Oro Division. I used a semi-structured online interview using the coding technique to analyze the data. The study disclosed different themes, such as difficulty building relationships and lack of consistency. Novice teachers may struggle with balancing building positive relationships and establishing themselves as authority figures in the classroom. They may fear being too strict or too lenient, which can impact their ability to set clear boundaries and manage the classroom effectively. Another theme was coping with the challenges in collecting results. Sub-themes were Clear communication and being Proactive. Engaging with colleagues and participating in collaborative activities, such as team-teaching or professional learning communities, can foster supportive relationships and provide opportunities for learning from others. While building relationships can be challenging for novice teachers, with time, experience, and intentional effort, they can develop meaningful connections that positively impact their teaching practice and student outcomes. Likewise, the incumbent school heads must understand the new curriculum in depth. Future studies can assist in developing successful techniques for supporting new teachers and enhancing student results in various educational environments by examining these and other issues relating to the experiences of novice teachers in a devolved working relationship with their school head. Overall, the study of the experiences of novice teachers with the devolved working relationship with their School Head has significant implications for developing effective strategies for supporting novice teachers.

KEY WORDS

1. novice teachers 2. devolved working conditions 3. responsibilities

Date Received: July 25, 2024 — Date Reviewed: August 01, 2024 — Date Published: September 2, 2024

1. Introduction

As an instructional leader, the school head actively promotes more effective teaching and learning practices and recognizes instructional priorities rather than serving as a school manager. The school head, who may be assisted by an assistant school head, shall be both an

instructional leader and an administrative manager. The school head shall form a team with the school teachers/learning facilitators to deliver quality educational programs, projects, and services. They establish learning as the core of their practice and set the tone, direction, and expectations for learning in the school based on what they pay attention to, what they do, and what they reward. The school heads, as learners, set individual learning goals for themselves. The school heads play a crucial role in building a positive and professional school culture and learning environment, a responsibility that significantly influences teacher retention. The principal's day-to-day work and values-driven behavior form a set of positive underlying norms, values, and beliefs that drive learning. It acts as either a support or a deterrent for teacher retention. Further scrutiny reveals just how powerful working conditions influence the retention of all teachers, as demonstrated by the following observations. In the international context in supporting the quality of education or education standards, Khanal (2018) argues, "School principal leadership plays a significant role in school success through its effects on teachers' perception, attitudes, and behaviors. In the same way, to create a different performance of improvement in a school, the principal's role plays an essential tool (Anderson, 2008). As each principal is a crucial agent in a school, they should play a key role in adopting strategically well-trained staff management. The principal is believed to be a team leader who assures the staff is strongly dedicated to understanding the school's goals (Moindi et al., 2016). According to Mahlangu (2014); and Mestry (2017), principals in the 21st century must execute multi-faceted roles to achieve the targeted goals that the schools have expected. Several research studies emphasize the importance of principals taking on strong leadership in establishing well-equipped schools. Principals usually perform three compatible roles: manager,

leader, and administrator at the school level. Managers focus on managing and monitoring human, physical, and financial resources. Leaders drive the school's vision and focus on organizational development and school improvement. At the same time, administrators deal with day-to-day operational matters and continuously modify leadership and management functions. Recognized as the school's leader, the principal is expected to continually facilitate student success and school improvement. According to Akinfolarin and Emetarom (2017), management support practices are geared toward providing a friendly climate for workers' productivity. Nwite (2016) defined management support practices as enabling a work environment for teachers to render the needed services effectively in the school system. Nwite further pointed out that management support practices include supervision, motivation, professional growth, and welfare. Also, Akinfolarin and Emetarom (2017) highlighted management support practices in schools, including providing supervision and motivation, ensuring staff professional development, and applying other supportive management functions to improve instructional delivery or attaining school goals and objectives. The management support practices adopted by the above authors in this study are professional development and staff welfare. The persistent increase in the demand for quality instructional delivery processes requires professional competencies on the part of the teachers. Similarly, Ezeugbor (2015) noted that teaching is a public service that requires exceptional expertise, knowledge, and specialized skills sustained through vigorous and continuous professional development. As opined by Werner and Desimone (2012), professional development is a set of systematic and planned activities designed by an organization to allow its members to learn the necessary skills to meet current and future demands. Professional development allows teachers to acquire additional competen-

cies and qualifications to perform their teaching job successfully. It instills confidence in the teaching profession, thus advancing teachers' careers. Several professional development practices could enhance teachers' job performance. Among others are symposiums, continuous training and retraining, workshops, research opportunities, conferences, and study leave for refresher courses. Similar to this, Abdulrahman (2015) pointed out that staff professional development practices through seminar, in-service training or workshops offer one of the most promising ways to improve classroom instruction. Organizing in-service training for teachers helps to equip them with emerging trends and strategies in the teaching profession. Azaru, Syed, and Muhammad (2013) defined training as the process of improving the existing skills, knowledge, exposure, and abilities of an individual. It is a process designed to expose teachers to new approaches and trends in education in order to equip them with the required skills. Althassan (2014) argued that in-service training for teachers has been one of the significant practices of school heads in developing their teachers. The principal is responsible for providing management support practices in the area of training and re-training of teachers to enable them to discharge their instructional delivery tasks professionally. In the local context, particularly in Davao City, Ingay (2019) stressed that the Literature review on the teachers' morale being influenced by school heads' leadership practice and work ethics is limited and the study would be an attempt to fill the gap on the topic in Davao City, thereby making the study at hand important and timely. The study was conducted to determine the baseline data relative to the leadership practice and work commitment of elementary school heads will

be gauged to identify the school heads' leadership practices and work commitment as determinants of teachers' morale. Republic Act No. 9155, Chapter 1 Section No. 7, Letter E, Paragraph 3 stated that, consistent with the national educational policies, plans, and standards, the school heads shall have the Authority, Responsibility, and Accountability (AuRA) to manage all school affairs. Thus, the success or failure of the school depends on the kind of school principal it has. These authors confirm that principals are expected to establish appropriate preconditions for effective teaching and learning and to follow through with interventions aimed at improving teaching and learning. The quality of education in every school seems to rely heavily on the principal's contribution to ensuring a healthy organization geared towards achieving high standards of teaching and learning. However, there is no available research in the Division of Davao De Oro concerning devolving work responsibilities of school heads. In other words, it is fair to state that the concept of organizational health has not yet been introduced in Davao De Oro literature because there were previously no studies on schools' devolving work responsibilities of school heads as narrated by novice teachers of teachers in the division. Indeed, it was hoped that exploring these interactions would serve as an avenue for digesting progress in the school management system, which is essential in making the school a community development resource. In enhancing the educational conditions, whatever findings that this study may have, would surely be disseminated during divisional assemblies, conventions, and research forums so as to contribute to an improved delivery of educational public service for the development of the school community.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this study was to explore the experiences of teachers in a working condition where delegation is present in their pursuit to support their well-being. This includes the highlights and challenges of their pursuit and also the coping practices to

overcome challenges. Moreover, it explores how the school manages and delivers its/function in the school development. And try to understand the competencies that school heads need to possess include school leadership, instructional leadership, creating a student-centered learning climate, human resource management and professional development, parent involvement and community partnership, school management and operations, personal and professional attributes

1.2. Research Questions—This phenomenological study aimed to describe teachers’ experiences in devolved working conditions and their good working environment with this new normal. to the success of a learner’s education. Furthermore, this study sought to answer the following questions: The study aims to answer the following questions specifically:

- (1) What are the experiences of novice teachers in the devolved working responsibilities of their school heads?
- (2) How do the teachers cope with the challenges in the devolved working responsibilities of their school heads?
- (3) enumerate

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms were defined conceptually and operationally for better understanding of the readers: Novice teachers were described as teachers in their first year of teaching with little or no prior teaching experience. Unless exempted by their principal, novices are required to participate in the Induction and Mentoring Program. Novices meet weekly with their mentor(s) regarding lesson plans, management, instruction, etc. Devolved working conditions. Devolution was the

transfer of powers and funding from national to local government. It was important because it ensured that decisions were made closer to the local people, communities, and businesses they affected. Responsibilities were the state or fact of being responsible, answerable, or accountable for something within one’s power, control, or management. An instance of being responsible was: The responsibility for this mess was yours! A particular burden of obligation upon one who was responsible was the responsibility of authority.

1.4. Significant of the Study—The highlights of this study will be significant to the following: Teachers are given the critical role that teachers play in the lives of children, young adults, and wider society; their working conditions must be supported to prevent issues, and help is provided when problems do arise. This was furthermore significant to the learners, as teachers’ work-

ing conditions adversely affect students’ levels of achievement. Additionally, this was significant to the school heads, for it could be a reference as to how to cope with the teacher’s challenges in the workplace and how to address them as the school leader. Lastly, to fellow educational researchers, this study could reference similar and comparative studies.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored in the theory of Frederick Taylor, The Scientific Management Scientific The-

ory. Taylor started the Scientific Management movement, and he and his associates were the first to study the work process scientifically. They studied how work was

performed and looked at how this affected worker productivity. Taylor's philosophy focused on the belief that making people work as hard as possible was not as efficient as optimizing how the work was done. In 1909, Taylor published "The Principles of Scientific Management." In this, he proposed that productivity would increase by optimizing and simplifying jobs. He also advanced the idea that workers and managers needed to cooperate. This was very different from how work was typically done in businesses beforehand. A factory manager at that time had very little contact with the workers, and he left them on their own to produce the necessary product. There was no standardization, and a worker's primary motivation was often continued employment, so there was no incentive to work as quickly or efficiently as possible. Taylor believed that all workers were motivated by money, so he promoted the idea of "a fair day's pay for a fair day's work." In other words, if a worker did not achieve enough in a day, he did not deserve to be paid as much as another highly productive worker. Another theory relevant to this study was the Systems Approach to management theory, commonly viewed as the foundation of organizational development. This theory views the organization as an open system of interrelated and interdependent parts that interact as subsystems. Thus, the organization comprises a unified singular system made up of these subsystems. Meanwhile, I adopted the Behavioral Theory of leadership (Watson, 1913), which is a big leap from Trait Theory in that it assumes that leadership capability can be learned rather than inherent. This theory is based on the principle that behaviors can be conditioned in a manner that one can have a specific response to specific stimuli. Rather than seeking inborn traits, this theory looks at what leaders actually do by studying their

behaviors in response to different situations, assessing leadership success by studying their actions, and then correlating significant behaviors with success. The practical application of the theory is that a leader's behavior affects their performance, and different leadership behaviors could be appropriate at different times. The best leaders are those who have the adaptability to flex their behavioral style and choose the right style suitable for each situation. According to this theory, people can learn to become leaders through teaching and observation and certain behavioral patterns may be identified as leadership styles. Behavioral theory promotes the value of management with an emphasis on concern for people and collaboration. It promotes participative decision-making and team development by supporting individual needs and aligning individual and group objectives. It helps managers evaluate and understand how their behavioral style as a manager affects their relationship with the team and promotes commitment and contribution towards organizational goals. This theory helps managers find the right balance between different styles of leadership and helps them decide how to behave as a leader, depending on concerns for people and productivity (Technofunc, 2013). Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. It shows three interconnected working themes. The experiences of novice teachers in a devolved working responsibility of their school heads., a qualitative inquiry that allows researchers and teachers as well as learners to provide the necessary skills, knowledge, and focus on engaging in meaningful inquiry about their professional practice would enhance this practice and effect positive changes concerning the educative goals of the learning community. The first circle, which interlinks to the second circle, shows a genuine concern; however,

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

the center of the two circles determines that there is a way of exploring how teachers cope with challenges in a devolved working responsibility of their school heads, a way of teaching and learning development that is critical to school success. Their intersection was the educational management insight drawn from the study.

2. Methodology

Presented in this chapter were the description of the research design, philosophical assumptions, research participants and sampling, ethical consideration, research instrument, data collection, and data analysis. There are at least three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) was optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics were being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry which asks the questions, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people? The goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of the school heads in the new normal as they try to compare its implementation then and now. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—

This research study would use a phenomenological research design using exploratory: for the facets of information derived from fluid, subjective, and taken from the experiences and perspectives of the participants, which were most suitable for exploratory study. This design would begin with assumptions and use an interpretive framework that conforms to the research problems in addressing the perception of individuals or groups transcribed to a human social problem. The underlying philosophical assumptions of this research were identified. To study this problem, the researcher would use an emerging phenomenological inquiry, collecting data in a natural setting sensitive to the people and places under, and data analysis that was both inductive and deductive established patterns of themes. The final written report or presentation would include participants' experiences, the reflexivity of a complex description and interpretation of the problem, and its contribution to the literature or a call for change. The underlying philosophical assumptions that constituted the validity of this research were identified: Ontology, epistemology, axiology, and rhetoric (Creswell, 2012). Ontological assumptions refer to multiple realities that could be explored and constructed through human interactions and meaningful actions. These were observed as the actual words of participants. Their narrations of different experiences and responses were carefully taken and later analyzed. It was concerned with the nature of reality. Given the complexity of the world within which nursing research is conducted, researchers using qualitative methodologies have had to grapple with this issue. This was the view that there was a reality independent of the researcher which could be known. In this study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through

extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. I ensured that the participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemological assumptions would also be used to gain knowledge about the accessibility of the place. Knowledge is gained through an empathic understanding of participants' lived social realities; science aims to describe people's subjective lived realities, experiences, and understandings. Conducting a qualitative study means researchers try to get as close as possible to the studied participants. Therefore, subjective evidence is assembled based on individual views. This was how knowledge is known—through the subjective experiences of people. Guba and Lincoln (1985), as cited by Creswell (2013), state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an "insider." Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). I would identify phenomenology using thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief." This study intends to gather information from the participants regarding how they implemented the program following the guidelines set by DepEd and the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF). I assured that I would establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, partic-

ularly on the school's experiences and coping strategies in implementing the program in the new normal. This study would further use the axiological assumption for the "value-laden" experiences. The researcher's subjective values, intuition, and biases were important. They play a role in the dialog of social construction and inform his or her interpretation of the data. Often, at a less abstract level, these philosophical assumptions inform our choice of theories that guide our research. Qualitative researchers have underscored the importance of understanding the beliefs and theories that inform our research and actively writing about them in our reports and studies. Finally, personal, informal, and engaging language was used to advance the assumption of the rhetorical aspect of the study. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with participants' interpretation. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the

study. Therefore, I preserve the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpret them in light of their interpretations. Rhetorical Assumption No matter what type of research you are doing, the overall rhetorical assumption in qualitative research is that you are not "truth-seeking" or omniscient but instead reporting reality through the eyes of your research participants. The Rhetoric of Research Rhetoric is the art of speaking or writing effectively. It generally refers to how language is employed, but it has come to mean the insincere or manipulative use of words. The phenomenological design interprets the experiences or facts by listening to the participants' experiences and providing the meaning of those experiences (Creswell, 2007). It describes the structures of experiences as they present themselves to consciousness without recourse to theory, deduction, or assumption from other disciplines. The design examines the phenomena through the subjective eyes of the participants, which describes the meaning of the experiences of several individuals regarding a concept or phenomenon (Creswell, 2007).

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology was a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the experiences of the learners from grade one to grade six who were officially enrolled in Maniki Central Elementary School in the Division of Davao Del Norte were gathered through an in-depth interview (IDI) as well, and their coping strategies were extracted from the participants. The researcher's inquisitiveness on the experiences of the School

became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias (2013), considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena." By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the teachers and learners so that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to

Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs (2006), experience is a source of knowledge that shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap critical insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). According to Hancock et al. (2009), qualitative research answers ques-

tions regarding the issues involving societal problems. It raises the question of why people behave as they do, the possible opinions and attitudes formed in a particular situation, how people are affected by society in their ways of action, and how the practices and culture in the society developed. By using phenomenology, which is concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher hoped that the subjective experiences and perspectives of the participants would provide highlights as to how the program was implemented before COVID-19 and how it is currently executed.

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study utilized a qualitative phenomenological research design. The phenomenological design describes the participants' interpretations of their experiences. The participants were required to respond to the questions provided to them via Google Forms. Afterward, they were requested to participate in a Focus Group Discussion virtually and face to face, depending on the situation. At the end of this study, themes and common patterns were extracted from their responses (JamonCabanes, 2019). They decided to use a qualitative phenomenological research design because they would dwell on the individual experiences of the teachers under the new normal in Philippine public education. There were ten school heads as study participants who had firsthand experiences in the new normal in Philippine public education. The data gathered were recorded, transcribed, and validated to extract firsthand experiences on the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the new normal in Philippine public education from the secondary teachers' lived experiences. The Colaizzi method of data analysis was

used in a phenomenological research design. This is purely academic. The participants signed the informed consent, and this study has no risk. They could withdraw anytime as a participant in the study. Ethical considerations and safety health protocols were followed. Phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The approach's fundamental goal is to describe the nature of the particular phenomenon (Creswell, 2013). Typically, interviews are conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994): What have you experienced regarding the phenomenon? What contexts or situations have typically influenced your experiences of the phenomenon (Creswell, 2013)? Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, may also be used. The data is then read and reread, and culled for phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this process, the researcher may construct the

universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Some philosophical assumptions are employed in the development of research methodology. Subjective evidence gathered from field investigations was the subject of epistemological assumptions that deal with subjective evidence. Subjective evidence collected from field studies has also been used to gain knowledge brought by the accessibility of the place. Axiological assumptions account for the researcher's biases and actively report them; they were used to determine whether the investigated environment results from the behavior seen. Ontological assumptions refer to the nature of the reality of the subject being researched. The latter assumption was best suited to my study, for

as a qualitative researcher, I believe that different individuals perceive these realities. I also believe that these realities were heavily shaped by their experiences. The phenomenological design interprets the experiences or facts by listening to the participants' experiences and providing the meaning of those experiences (Creswell, 2007). It describes the structures of experiences as they present themselves to consciousness, without recourse to theory, deduction, or Epistemology rhetoric assumption from other disciplines. The design examines the phenomena through the subjective eyes of the participants, which describes the meaning of the experiences of several individuals regarding a concept or phenomenon (Creswell, 2007).

2.4. Research Participants—Purposive sampling was applied to the selection of the research participants. Purposive sampling is a sampling technique in which the researcher relies on his or her judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in the study. It is a non-probability sampling method, and it occurs when elements selected for the sample are chosen by the researcher's judgment. Researchers often believe they can obtain a representative sample by using sound judgment, saving time and money (Black, 2010). In this study, suitable samples include public school teachers, either male or female teachers, in Tagbaro Elementary School in the Division of Davao De Oro. Ten informants were part of the in-depth interview. Moreover, coding was used to protect the participants' identities. IDI-FT1 to IDI-FT7

were used for the informants of the in-depth interview. In this study, I played various roles in attaining the study's success. First, I would ask for permission to conduct the study, which would start with the Schools Division Superintendent and then go to my study participants. As a researcher, if consented, I would have to record the actual interview to achieve the needs of this type of research. The interview aims to better understand the learners' experiences in the new usual way of teaching and learning. The interview would also include how the Department of Education should improve its programs. After gathering the needed data, the researcher transcribed and analyzed everything. However, human instruments are more important to study in case the quality of this research has to deal with biases and assumptions regarding the persons involved (Greenbank, 2003).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—

Creswell (2007) emphasized that qualitative researchers face many ethical issues that surface during data collection in the field and analysis and dissemination of qualitative reports. In this study, the researcher deals with teachers in public schools. To ensure an authentic response from the participants, the researcher would be responsible for exercising extra caution and maintaining the confidentiality of the study. The rights of the participants were highly considered. Besides, they would not be forced to be part of the study when they refused. In protecting the identity of the participants, Glesne and Peshkins (1992) suggested that providing and assigning numbers or aliases can protect the anonymity of the participants. In this study, I used codes to protect the identity of the participants. Added to this, as the researcher, I explained the purpose and significance of the study. The participants were allowed to ask the researcher questions about the nature of the study. This certifies that the information was clear to the participants. Moreover, the participants' data gathering and participation are guided by the Informed Consent Form, which the chosen participants sign. Lastly, the results and findings were presented to the participants for verification. The transcriptions of the recorded interview were kept private. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process. They could be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. This would provide the participants with the opportunity to amend or remove any information that they feel might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to use pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates to protect the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the

Researcher. The researcher would ensure that he or she possesses the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher should complete the academic requirements and pass the comprehensive examination before thesis writing, which is the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher should also be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher would strive to complete the study successfully at the specified time and that he or she is equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee would help enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. Also, the researcher would ensure that he or she has enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, it was hoped that this study would be completed at the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher respected the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study would not involve any use of deceit at any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher would express great pleasure for the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher would respect other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said his or her way. The researcher would also always use quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher would ensure that honesty was present when working on the manuscript and that no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data and results were included or purposefully

putting forward conclusions that were not accurate.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—In this study, I used an Interview Guide Question Tool with sub-questions for the in-depth online interview. The tool was used as my guide while interviewing the selected teachers who would be my participants in the recorded in-depth online interview. This aimed to answer the research questions and collect additional inputs that could be useful in my study. To address the validity issues of this design, specifically the method, I would ask for help from the experts. The experts checked and validated my interview guide question tool. The sampling that was used for the selection of my participants was based on the suggestions of the expert panels. In the identification of these research informants, there were ten (10) public school heads of Forty-five (45) to Sixty (60) years old, either male or female, from the School Division of Davao Del Norte.

2.7. Data Collection—When gathering data, strict compliance with IATF protocols was observed. The researcher would secure a letter of permission from the participants and send it via email. Upon approval, the researcher would use the data collection forms as prescribed in the qualitative design. In this study, recording an in-depth interview and focus group discussion has been used. The researcher needs to understand the subjective interaction between the study participants. The researcher heavily relied on naturalistic methods such as interviewing and audio recording, and the interpretive paradigm was used. Interpretive approaches rely heavily on naturalistic methods like interviewing, observation, and analysis of existing texts. These methods ensure

Purposive sampling was used, especially exemplified through the vital informant technique wherein one or a few individuals were solicited to act as guides to a culture (Tongco, 2007). I used a referral system so that I could access teachers who would help qualify my criteria. This system was also called snowball sampling. Snowball sampling is a non-probability-based sampling technique used to gain access to such populations. The participants were purposely chosen so that the information needed could expedite the study. However, the application of snowball sampling would later be appropriated to gather the exact data needed to answer the research questions. Moreover, the identity of my participants will be strictly valued and respected under the "ethics of research." Hence, the researcher's interactions with them were collegial and morally upright.

an adequate dialog between the researchers and those with whom they interact to construct a meaningful reality collaboratively. Yin, as cited by Aquilam (2014), suggested numerous forms of data collection, including documents, archival records, interviews, direct observation, participant observation, and physical artifacts. To obtain legitimate and trustworthy data on teachers' experiences with the new usual way of teaching and learning, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview and focus group discussion. This interview aims to gather information on learners' feelings and experiences. The participants were encouraged to express their answers in the most comfortable manner. The interview has been transcribed word for word. Lastly, the researcher analyzed

the data collected using discourse analysis and thematic analysis. Creswell (2007) suggested that to succeed in the study, the data must be stored so that they could be easily found and protected from damage and loss. Furthermore, Interviews has also strengths and weaknesses. One of the strengths of an interview is that the interviews provide helpful information when participants cannot be directly observed. The interviewer has better control over the types of information that they receive. They could also pick their questions. If worded effectively, questions would encourage unbiased and

truthful answers. However, one of the weaknesses is that the interviewee may provide biased information or be unreliable if only one interviewer was interpreting the information. The best research requires many different points of view. The answers may be deceptive because the interviewee tries to respond in a way that would please the interviewer. Then, equipment may be costly and require a high level of technical competence to be used, and it could be time-consuming, and inexperienced interviewers may not be able to keep the questions properly focused (Quad, 2016).

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In analyzing the qualitative data, I have used discourse analysis and thematic analysis. Discourse analysis focuses on the language use and patterning of language used by the study's informants, as reflected in the detailed transcripts of recorded speech (Bueno, 2016). The recorded in-depth interview and focus group discussion will be transcribed and analyzed. Part of the analysis was to determine the

challenges, coping mechanisms, and leadership behavior of female school leaders. Thematic analysis was a method of identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns within data (Braun Clarke, 2006). It was a widely used method of analysis in qualitative research. In this study, I looked for patterns and themes that were generated in the transcribed in-depth interview and focus group discussion.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The second group includes methods independent of theory and epistemology, which could be applied across a range of different theoretical and epistemological approaches and are, therefore, very flexible. One such method is thematic analysis, which, through theoretical freedom, “provides flexible and useful research tool, which can potentially provide a rich and detailed, yet complex account of data (Braun Clark, 2006). I observed several steps in conducting a thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight.

I relied on my own resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I spent several nights listening to the interviews to deepen my understanding of the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated themselves to lay out the conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step is data extrac-

tion and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note-taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used many different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. I used forms of thematic grids and charts, the framework technique as developed by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al., 2003). This technique was helpful to me in the process of coding, sorting, and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was very useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedures included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross-referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke

(2006) consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. Phase 1. I familiarized myself with the data by reading the whole data set and noting down initial ideas; Phase 2. I generated initial codes, with code being the most basic segments of the raw data that can identify a feature of the data that appears interesting; Phase 3. I searched for themes by sorting different codes into potential themes and collated all data extracts within identified themes; Phase 4. I reviewed the themes and refined them further (at the level of coded data extracts and the entire data set) and produced a thematic map showing relationships between themes and sub-themes; Phase 5. I defined and named themes, making sure they gave the reader an immediate sense of what the theme was all about. Phase 6. I wrote the report to convince the reader of the merit and validity of the analysis (within and across the themes) and used data extracts embedded within an analytic narrative to make arguments in relation to the research question.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The concepts of validity and reliability are relatively foreign to the field of qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substitute data trustworthiness. Trustworthiness consists of the following components: credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility contributes to a belief in the trustworthiness of data by observing the attributes of prolonged engagement. To address the issue of credibility, interviewed as many research participants as possible or up to the point of saturation. Transferability was concerned with the extent to which the findings of one study can be applied to other situations. In positivist work, the concern often lies in

demonstrating that the results of the work at hand can be applied to a wider population since the findings of a qualitative project are specific to a small number of particular environments and individuals. It was impossible to demonstrate that the findings and conclusions apply to other situations and populations. Therefore, to ensure transferability, I acknowledged that it was my responsibility as a researcher to ensure sufficient contextual transformation about the fieldwork sites to enable the reader to make such a transfer. Confirmability associates objectivity in science with the use of instruments that are not dependent on human skill and perception. It was, however, challenging to ensure absolute objectivity since, as even tests and questionnaires are designed

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

by humans, the intrusion of the researcher's biases is inevitable. Here, steps must be taken to help ensure as far as possible that the work's findings were the result of the ex-

periences and ideas of the participants rather than the characteristics and preferences of the researcher.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from analyzing the interview data. It presents themes that emerge from the analysis. Along with the themes are comprehensive discussions that answer the objectives of the study. Before I begin my discussion, I established the symbols I used as I present the quotations based on the responses of the participants of the study. In reference to the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, I used pseudonyms to refer to participants of the research.

3.1. Experiences of Novice Teachers in a Devolved Working Responsibilities of their School Heads—The first objective of this study is to identify the experiences of Novice Teachers in the devolved working

responsibilities of their School Head. From the interviews conducted, the teachers' experiences were that building relationships is very challenging, and there is a lack of consistency, especially in the implementation of the policies and practices.

3.1.1. Difficulty in Building Relationships—The first theme in the teachers' experiences of devolved working responsibilities of the School Head is the difficulty in building relationships between the School Head and the novice teacher. The profile of the novice teacher is no longer exclusively defined as the recent graduate from a formal teacher preparation program. Johnson (2004) describes the new wave of novice 9 teachers as, "more homogeneous in race and gender than the retiring generation, more diverse in terms of age, prior experience, preparation, expectations regarding the workplace, and conceptions of career" (p. 7). Research conducted for the U.S. Department of Education by Goldring, Gray, and Bitterman (2013) found that 82% While the demographics of the teaching force have not shifted dramatically, there has been a shift in the quality of the teacher preparation programs completed by the current population of teachers. No Child Left Behind

(NCLB) "challenged the traditional concept of teaching by emphasizing content mastery and verbal ability, downplaying pedagogy as a less powerful determinant of student achievement," which led to changes in many teacher preparation programs (Blanton, Sindelar, Correa, 2006). As a result, NCLB policies created an increased demand to replace underperforming teachers, which sparked the creation of non-traditional entry points into the teaching career. Addressing the shift in teacher preparation, Darling-Hammond (2006) states that "teacher education as an enterprise has probably launched more new weak programs that underprepared teachers, especially for urban schools than it has further developed the stronger models that demonstrate what intense preparation can accomplish." Nearly 40% According to Henke, Chen, and Geis, (2000), 29% Although these novice teachers bring a variety of experiences, "mid-career entrants often enter their new school expecting a work-

place that was better equipped, more flexible, and more committed to their success than the one they found”. Novice teachers, at a unique phase in their profession, between theory and fully developed practice, are entering a profession vastly different from previous generations (Johnson, 2004). While Johnson focused on teachers in years one and two of their careers, she emphasizes the variation in workplace expectations as they enter the profession. For instance, since the 1960s, a wider range of career options has become available to women. Many of these professions provided a substantial improvement in compensation and training. This has elevated the expectations novice teachers have for support as they enter the teaching profession. This is in contrast to the increasing demands placed on new teachers. Johnson (2012), posits that novice teachers are “expected to teach all students so that they achieve high standards and to take on new functions beyond the traditional scope of school’s responsibility. Johnson also states “school structures and practices are no longer adequate to support either teachers’ development or students’ learning. Fantilli and McDougall (2009) identify several challenges that novice teachers experience in their first few years. Significant challenges include difficult teaching assignments, limited or no school support, inadequate traditional and non-traditional preparation programs, an emphasis on student preparation to pass high-stakes assessments, and limited skills in differentiating instruction for exceptional students. Johnson (2004) presents the challenge to public schools as follows: An issue of great concern to policymakers, practitioners, and the public is the challenge of ensuring that all students, wherever they are and wherever they live, have good teachers. If schools fail to attract and retain a strong, committed cohort of new teachers in the coming years, students will be severely penalized, and those in low-income communities will be likely to pay the greatest price. Yet, despite the challenges new teachers face, novice teachers directly impact students, their learning, and the culture of the school. While growing a population of experienced teachers is imperative for the teaching profession, this work must be embedded within a system of support that recognizes and encourages and is equipped to develop teachers with the pedagogical and content skills to meet the needs of all students (Andrews et al., 2007; Brock Grady, 1998; Hallinger, 2011). Factors Influencing Novice Teacher Job Satisfaction According to Shann (1998), “Teacher job satisfaction has been shown to be a predictor of teacher retention, a determinant of teacher commitment, and in turn, a contribution to school effectiveness” (p. 67). Yet, there is a range of factors related to teacher job satisfaction, and these factors may vary over time, reflecting organizational and cultural changes (Rhodes et al., 2004; Shreeve et al., 2018). According to Shreeve et al., “factors of job satisfaction shift with the times and fluctuate with the mores, in effect reflecting facets of the changing culture. The MetLife Survey of American Teachers (Markow, Macia, Lee, 2013) examined teacher job satisfaction and how the factors of job satisfaction change over time. Teacher job satisfaction rose from 40 in 1984 to reach a high of 62 in 2009. However 2012, teacher satisfaction declined to 39, the lowest point since 1986 (Markow et al., 2013). Based on the third domain of teacher satisfaction, the next section of the literature identifies factors that influence the job satisfaction of novice teachers. Intrinsic and extrinsic motivators are specifically connected to working conditions, teacher pedagogical practice,

self-efficacy, and teacher autonomy.

3.1.2. Lack of Consistency—Another challenge for novice teachers in the devolved working responsibilities of the school head is the lack of consistency. Devolving responsibilities to multiple staff members can result in inconsistency in the implementation of the policies and practices. This can be confusing for novice teachers who may not understand why different approaches are being used in different classrooms. The participants shared that a lack of consistency will not help them improve their professional growth. The first years of teaching are a period of intense transition as novice teachers take on the responsibilities of planning instruction, teaching, assessing students, and managing a classroom while also encountering “incompatible notions of the best means by which to teach. The student-centered theories and pedagogical approaches novice teachers have studied in their teacher preparation programs are often incongruent with the prescriptive and standardized institutional norms in schools in the United States. Smagorinsky et al. (2015) argued that “this conundrum helps explain why beginning teachers experience such dissonance when moving between universities and schools... when trying to develop for themselves a conception of effective instruction. This article reports findings from a study of a year-long professional development program that we implemented as part of our efforts to provide support for novice teachers that could help them learn to adapt in relation to the affordances and constraints of their instructional and institutional contexts. In particular, the authors draw upon findings from this study to address the pressing need for professional development programs that respond to the challenges novice teachers encounter in their specific teach-

ing contexts. The professional development program was designed to create opportunities for novice teachers to examine the kinds of challenges they encounter and provide a mechanism that might help them explore and learn from the underlying sources of tension within those struggles. We studied the implementation of this program to generate understandings that can inform efforts to re-imagine and improve the systems of support currently available for novice teachers. Our study of the implementation of this professional development program was guided by the following question: What kinds of challenges do novice teachers encounter and how might exploring those challenges in structured dialogue designed to position struggle as a source of growth inform approaches to professional development? We will discuss what we learned about the challenges novice teachers participating in this study encountered and their responses to them. We use that discussion to articulate the nuances within those challenges the data indexed in relation to the act of teaching and occupying the role of teacher in order to present recommendations for improving professional development programs. (all participants’ names are pseudonyms), who was in his third year of teaching at the time of this study, gave voice to one significant challenge he encountered related to the disconnect between the beliefs that informed his conceptions of teaching and the reality of his teaching context. He shared his struggle to reconcile his notions of what teaching would be with the reality he encountered with the other participants in this study by saying: “So, coming out of college, I had all these grandiose ideas. Like, these big ideas that I wanted to achieve in my students’ learning. I had a really hard

Fig. 3. Experiences of Novice Teachers in Devolved Working Responsibilities of Their School Heads

time transitioning into the actual classroom. These concerns echo those voiced by other novice teachers who have become frustrated by a disconnect between who they want to be as teachers and what is required of them by their teaching contexts (Barnes, 2018; Smagorinsky et al., 2004). A study by Fecho et al. (2021) highlighted the frustration that can occur as novice teachers experience conflict between their pedagogical goals and their teaching contexts. Elise, for example, wanted to be a teacher who could bring “content into dialogue with students’ lives”. Working from this stance, Elise created a unit of instruction on *Romeo and Juliet* designed “to lead her students in an exploration of how Shakespeare created characters and conflict” emphasis in the original). She believed the characters and the conflicts in this play would resonate with the personal experiences of the adolescent readers in her classroom. However, the pacing guides her school required her to follow constrained her ability to leverage those connections because it only allowed seven 90-minute class

periods to read this complex play. Elise felt she had to “rush through the text”. Without enough time to explore the play in the depth she felt was necessary, Elise became frustrated by what she deemed as her “failure to connect such a connectable play in a dialogical way. Our previous research in teacher education and teacher induction (Stewart, 2018; Stewart et al., 2019; Stewart Jansky, 2021) indicates that professional development approaches that explore the specific challenges that novice teachers encounter in their classrooms can help them develop novel ways to respond to those challenges. Findings from these studies pointed to how engaging in collaborative dialogue explored the participants’ specific contextual challenges and enabled them to work together to posit productive responses to struggles that increased their sense of agency and confidence. Figure 3 shows novice teachers’ experiences in their school head devolved working responsibilities and the emergence of the three themes: Difficulty in Building Relationships and Lack of Consistency.

3.2. Coping Mechanism of Novice Teachers to Address the Experience of devolved Working Responsibilities of their School Heads—

Another objective of the study is to explore the coping mechanisms of novice teachers regarding their experiences with devolved

working responsibilities. For this objective, the themes that were found were establishing clear communication.

3.2.1. *Establish clear communication*—

Novice teachers can establish clear communication with the School Head and other staff members who have been given devolved responsibilities. This can help to ensure that everyone is of the same age and working towards shared goals. There are and have always been conversations about schools and how they should be managed and lead to achieve good results. During the last few years, there has been increased attention on how to measure and understand what activities and actions lead to certain results. Research shows that schools and the individual teacher and principal make a difference (e.g. Day Leithwood, 2007; Grosin, 2003; Leithwood Riehl, 2003; Sammons, 2006). become prerequisites for what activities and perspectives are valued and lead to further actions. This implies that communication can be both a way to analyze and understand processes in schools and a process to influence others' actions and understanding. An ordinary working day for principals and teachers contains many meetings, interactions, and conversations. The question is, how do these activities contribute to school outcomes? Public organizations have specific objectives and aim to fulfill them. Schools in Sweden have a short and concentrated curriculum that requires local interpretation, which provides the actors with a wide range of opportunities to realize the national objectives (Utbildningsdepartementet, 2001). The schools shall rest on fundamental democratic values and use the school funding and resources as effective as possible. There are also expectations that principals and teachers in Swedish

school shall work with school improvement and constantly improve their activities and results in relation to how society changes and develops. This requires principals and teachers who are engaged, knowledgeable and have time to talk about issues related to teaching and learning. Even if communication often is described as important, a large part of everyday conversations and how they are conducted are taken for granted and are not consciously used (Heide, Clarén, Johansson, Simonsson, 2005; Miller, 2006). This can result in too many messages in the organization not coming through in the intended way (Kotter, 1996). According to the Swedish curriculum (2017) the principal has a key role that includes conducting pedagogical leadership. taking responsibility so that the work inside the school is focused on the national objectives. The principal contributes, consciously as well as unconsciously, to how structural, cultural and leadership processes develop. It is impossible to conduct any type of leadership without communication since leadership and communication are closely connected. If there weren't any meetings and conversations where principals could inform, share reflections, challenge, support and motivate the personnel the only way for a leader to affect followers would be reduced to rewards and punishments (Eriksen, 1998). A communicative leadership is especially important in organizations with values that are non-negotiable (Eriksen, 2001). Even if the principal takes part in different processes and, therefore, is affected by them, there are organizational expectations on how the leader shall contribute to these processes. Is

it possible to trace how principals contribute to the school's outcomes in the school's communication processes? One of the principal's challenges is to support teachers to improve student outcomes. What principals and teachers talk about and how they com-

municate both reflect and construct what is considered important in different processes and activities. Communication, therefore, also reveals what is in focus in the organization's everyday work.

3.2.2. Be Proactive—Another theme under the coping mechanism of teachers is being proactive. The participants shared that this can help to build their confidence and establish a sense of ownership over their work. Proactive personality can significantly predict academic engagement. Students with proactive personalities are more likely to succeed than passive students. Proactive individuals tend to scan for opportunities and look for all possibilities to utilize resources and shape the environment. They have a higher level of persistence, demonstrate initiative to overcome difficulties from unexpected environments, and involve themselves in fulfilling their ambitions (Hu et al., 2020). It found that students with a higher level of proactive personality were less likely to disengage and used fewer avoidant strategies to reduce effort or give up in stressful situations. Moreover, Zhu et al. (2017) found that proactive students reported higher academic performance in stressful situations than passive students. In addition, Islam et al. (2018) found students who had a proactive personality undertook more responsibility in academic citizenship behavior and helped other students engage in extracurricular activities. A stable tendency to observe and understand the world may have an effect on how students perceive teacher behavior (Charalampous and Kokkinos, 2014). Previous research has shown that different personalities traits foster different teacher-student relationships (Zee et al., 2013; Charalampous and Kokki-

nos, 2014). Kokkinos (2014) found that students with high levels of extraversion experience more teacher proximity, while those with high levels of neuroticism experience less. Furthermore, their research also found that perceiving teacher proximity had an effect on students' achievement and simultaneously mediated the relationship between personality traits and students' achievement. According to MRC, "behavior, cognition, and other personal factors, and environmental influences, all operate as interacting determinants that influence each other bidirectionally" (Bandura, 1989, p. 2). Personal factors may influence individuals' behavior, as well as how they perceive the environment. Teacher-student relationships, as a crucial role in helping students to solve problems, may be a potential candidate. Teacher-student relationships refer to students' sense that they have positive interactions with their teachers, and that their teachers are supportive of their learning needs (Collie et al., 2016). A large number of studies found that teacher-student relationships were associated with academic engagement (Gehlbach et al., 2012; Pianta et al., 2012; Varga, 2017; Hughes and Cao, 2018). As students spend at least one-quarter of their waking time in school, teacher-student relationships provide the potential for classroom resources and catalyze important benefits for student engagement in class (Hughes et al., 2008). Numerical research has also well documented the relationship between teacher-student rela-

tionships and academic engagement across different educational contexts and ethnicities (Den Brok et al., 2010; Christenson et al., 2012; Pianta et al., 2012). Moreover, Chen and Astor (2011) recruited more than 14,000 students from Taiwan and found that students with negative personalities were less likely to build teacher-student relationships, which further inhibited students engaging in learning. Proactive personality may be a key internal factor in dealing with teacher-student relationships. Theoretically, students with proactive personalities may actively ask teachers questions, share life experiences with teachers, obey classroom rules, and comply with class discipline to build good teacher-student relationships. However, to the best of our knowledge, no study explores the relationship between proactive personality and teacher-student relationships. There were several indirect evidences (Sanchez-Cardona et al., 2012; Charalampous and Kokkinos, 2014; Hua et al., 2020; Hu et al., 2020). For example, Hu et al. (2020) found that students with a proactive personality tend to show more psychological comfort, acquaintance there with social environment (i.e., like interacting with professors), and social adjustment. According to the social cognitive theory that individuals should be concerned “not with what one has, but with the belief in what one can do with whatever resources one can muster” to carry out tasks (Bandura, 2007), academic self-efficacy may be another mediator between proactive personality and academic engagement. Academic self-efficacy is defined as students’ judgment of their own capabilities to carry out school-related activities (Schunk, 2019), which equips students for powerful thinking and confidence (Bandura, 2016). Existing research revealed that academic self-efficacy was positively related to academic engagement (Ozkal, 2019). Students with high academic self-efficacy are more willing to spend extra energy and time to complete learning tasks; Thus, they concentrate more on school-related activities (Siu et al., 2014). Contrastingly, students with low self-efficacy tend to dwell on past mistakes and reduce their efforts when facing difficult tasks (Bandura, 1977). For example, Ozkal (2019) found that self-efficacy for learning could significantly predict academic engagement. Moreover, one study with 387 fifth-grade elementary school students indicated that if a student enters the classroom environment with strong internal resources (self-efficacy), the student may be well-equipped to face the challenges presented, resulting in more learning engagement (Martin Rimm-Kaufman, 2015). Additionally, Sanchez-Cardona et al. (2012) conducted longitudinal research and reported that from 37 students, those with higher openness traits tended to consider demands as challenges and used all available resources to promote engagement. Proactive personality can significantly predict academic self-efficacy (Lin et al., 2014; Hua et al., 2020). Students who have a higher level of proactive personality are more likely to build a strong belief that they can succeed, which contributes toward them achieving goals (Lin et al., 2014). For example, Lin et al. (2014) conducted a longitudinal study and found that students possessing highly proactive personalities were more likely to utilize available resources to improve situations and persistently achieve goals. Furthermore, they found that a proactive personality could predict later academic self-efficacy. Moreover, Hua et al. (2020) found that students with a proactive personality showed a higher level of adjustment self-efficacy, which further influenced their academic behavior. Figure 4 shows the coping mechanism with the

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanism with the Challenges in a Devolved Working Responsibilities of their School Head

challenges in the devolved working responsibilities of their school Head and the emergence of the two themes: Clear Communication, and Be Proactive.

3.3. *Insights Gained from the Study*—The study’s final goal is to conclude its findings. These conclusions were drawn from emerging themes in teacher experiences, such as difficulty building relationships and lack of consistency. One insight gained from the challenges and coping mechanisms in a devolved working responsibilities setting under the School Heads is the importance of establishing clear communication and being proactive as part of the School’s Organizational Chart. Clear communication is essential for ensuring that all teachers understand their roles and responsibilities, while collaboration can help ensure consistency in implementing policies and practices. Another

insight is the importance of being flexible. Novice teachers need to be proactive and flexible regarding approaches and strategies. This can help them adapt to changing circumstances and work effectively with the school’s policies and priorities. Overall, the challenges and coping mechanisms in devolved working responsibilities set under the School Head highlight the importance of communication, collaboration, proactivity, flexibility, seeking support, and focusing on student learning. By embracing this insight and strategies, novice teachers can effectively navigate their challenges and positively impact student learning and achievement.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study. It was followed by implications based on the study’s findings. Future directions are also discussed here.

4.1. *Findings*—The main objective of this study was to explore the experiences of novice teachers in the devolved working re-

sponsibilities of their School Head. This study also explored teachers’ coping mechanisms in addressing their program imple-

mentation challenges. Several results have been found. The results of the interviews showed that the participants were having difficulties building relationships with the School Head. Also, the participants shared that they experienced a lack of consistency in implementing the school's policies and guidelines. Another objective of this study was to explore teachers' coping mechanisms

for addressing their challenges with devolved working responsibilities. For this objective, the study's results showed that teachers employed alternative means like establishing better and clearer communication and being proactive to achieve harmonious and better results within academic and administrative operations.

4.2. Implications—The study of novice teachers' experiences with a devolved working relationship with their School Head has several implications. The novice teachers' experiences in their school head devolved working responsibilities and the emergence of the three themes: Difficulty in Building Relationships and Lack of Consistency. Difficulty in Building Relationships: The teacher-student relationship is seen by novices as nothing more than how teachers interact with students; it becomes challenging to see 'good' teacher-student relationships as anything other than innate personality traits that teachers either have or do not have if it was not personality, it was maybe seen as some 'act' that teachers put on for engagement. This perception creates problems for novice teachers and their development and must be addressed by leaders explicitly. If we leaders understand teacher-student relationships and ask novices to observe teachers that we perceive to have 'good' relationships with their classes towards replication, they were likely to struggle to break down what they looked into as tangible applications for their practice. The coping mechanism for the challenges in the devolved working responsibilities of their school Head and the emergence of the two themes: Clear Communication and Proactiveness. Lack of Consistency: The study could provide insights into the

Multiple staff members being given duties that can lead to inconsistent application of the policies and practices. This can perplex inexperienced teachers who might not comprehend the rationale for employing various methodologies in various classrooms. The participants agreed that inconsistent behavior will not advance their professional development. The student-centered theories and pedagogical approaches novice teachers have studied in their teacher preparation programs are often incongruent with the schools' prescriptive and standardized institutional norms. For the coping mechanisms, the following themes were: Clear Communication: The study can inform efforts. With the School Head and other staff members who have been granted devolved responsibility, novice teachers can create clear communication. By doing so, you can ensure every one is the same age and working for the same objectives. There have been and would continue discussions regarding how schools could be led and managed to produce positive results. How to quantify and comprehend what activities and actions result in specific consequences has received more attention in recent years. According to research, schools, as well as each teacher and principal, have an impact. The schools shall rest on fundamental democratic values and use the school funding and resources as effectively as possible. Be Proactive: The

study can provide insights into the impact of devolving responsibilities on student outcomes. A proactive personality can considerably predict academic engagement. Proactive students are more likely to succeed than passive ones. Proactive people often search for opportunities, consider all possible ways to use resources, and alter their surroundings. They are more persistent, show initiative to deal with challenges from unanticipated situations, and engage in activities to achieve their goals. It found that students with a higher level of proactive personality were less likely to disengage and used

fewer avoidant strategies to reduce effort or give up in stressful situations. The role of a principal in implementing new curricula includes but is not limited to the following: Ensure that all teaching staff are aware and trained in the new curriculum reforms. The incumbent principal also needs to acquire an in-depth understanding of the new curriculum. Overall, the study of novice teachers' experiences with a devolved working relationship with their School Head has significant implications for developing effective strategies for supporting novice teachers and improving student outcomes.

4.3. Future Directions—There are several potential future directions for studying the experiences of novice teachers in a devolved working relationship with their School Heads. Longitudinal studies: Future studies could examine the experiences of novice teachers over a more extended period, such as one or more school years. This could provide insights into how novice teachers' experiences change over time as they gain more experience and expertise. Cross-cultural studies: Further research could explore how novice teachers' experiences in a devolved working relationship with their School Head vary across different cultural contexts. This could provide insights into the cultural factors that influence the success of devolving responsibilities. Comparative studies: Future studies could compare the experiences of novice teachers in a devolved working relationship with their School Head to those of novice teachers in a traditional working relationship. This could provide insights into the

advantages and disadvantages of different teacher supervision and support approaches. Qualitative studies: Further research could explore the experiences of novice teachers in a devolved working relationship with their School Head using qualitative methods, such as interviews and focus groups. This could provide more in-depth insights into the challenges and opportunities of devolving responsibilities. Technology-based studies: Future studies could explore the use of technology in supporting novice teachers in a devolved working relationship with their School Head. This could include examining the effectiveness of online professional development programs, communication tools, and other technology-based interventions. By investigating these and other topics related to the experiences of novice teachers in a devolved working relationship with their school head, future research can help inform effective strategies for supporting novice teachers and improving student outcomes in diverse educational contexts.

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